

COMMERCIAL REAL ESTATE MARKET FORECASTING MODEL

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ANNOTATION

Econometric models play an important role among the macroeconomic models that are currently being developed and used to study economics. Economic events, as a rule, are determined simultaneously by a multitude of conciliatory and frequently occurring factors. In connection with this relationship, the task often arises to investigate whether one variable depends on more than one explanatory variable. This problem is solved using multivariate regression analysis.

The advantage of these models is the ability to quantify the interconnections of the system. The elements of this type of model are indicators of regression equations describing the dynamics of the economic system and its individual components with a certain probability through changes in indicators that determine economic processes.

Key words: commercial real estate market, rent, sale, entrepreneurship, market segment, correlation analysis, indicators of economic development.

The use of econometric models requires a qualitative analysis of the object of study, a causal interpretation of the conditions and results of the study, since the mathematical apparatus of regression analysis used gives only quantitative estimates. When making a prediction using regression models, it is necessary to decide how long a string should be selected for prediction. It can be seen that if the length of the range of economic dynamics is too small, its development trends may not be detected. On the other hand, very large time series may cover periods with different trends, and their description using a single equation may not give a positive result. For this reason, it is recommended to proceed as follows: if there are no considerations in the order of quality, it is necessary to take as long a time interval as possible. If the development determines a periodic character, it is necessary to take all conical cycles; if the series covers periods with different trends, it is desirable to shorten the line by excluding previous

levels with different development trends. Real estate is a set of material objects consisting of a land plot and elements firmly connected with it, including the subsurface content under it and the airspace above it, as well as buildings and structures. "The regional real estate market is directly dependent on the state of the region's economy as a whole. As the study shows, the main factors affecting the real estate market in the region are the following indicators:

Sectoral structure of the region's economy. The level of economic development (GRP) and the growth rate of GRP, the level of income of the population, the level of employment, the volume of investments, the ownership structure. Considering the impact of each of these factors, it can be noted that the real estate market of the region is formed and developed based on the needs of the region's economy. On the other hand, there is also a reverse influence, which is expressed by the possibility of a certain modification of the direction of economic development of the region based on the current state of the real estate market. Thus, in order to create an effective concept for the development of the region, local authorities must determine the full range of its features, in particular the real estate market, and create an effective system of regulation of economic activity for the optimal development of all aspects of the life of the region. Based on the comparison of the main indicators affecting the real estate market, it is possible to give a comparative characteristic of the regional real estate market in relation to other regions. Such an approach makes it possible to assess the preference of a particular region from the position of the state and prospects of the real estate market development over other regions. Considering the impact of each of these factors, it can be noted that the real estate market of the region is formed and developed based on the needs of the region's economy. On the other hand, there is also a reverse influence, which is expressed by the possibility of a certain modification of the direction of economic development of the region based on the current state of the real estate market. Thus, in order to create an effective concept for the development of the region, local authorities must determine the full range of its features, in particular the real estate market, and create an effective system of regulation of economic activity for the optimal development of all aspects of the life of the region. Based on the comparison of the main indicators affecting the real estate market, it is possible to give a comparative characteristic of the regional real estate market in relation to other regions. Such an approach makes it possible to assess the preference of a particular region from the position of the state and prospects of the real estate market development over other regions.

Modern market conditions presuppose as the main principle of the development of the real estate market the freedom of economic decision-making by market participants. However, the role of the state does not come to naught. In the new conditions, the state becomes the largest participant in the real estate market, and also retains certain (albeit to a lesser extent) regulatory functions. Using administrative and economic mechanisms of influence on the real estate market, the state is called upon to ensure equal conditions for all participants in economic activity, freedom of decision-making and responsibility for the results of its activities. The state impact on the real estate market has the following objectives: - to promote the progressive crisis-free development of the real estate sector, which is expressed in the production of real estate objects sufficient for the needs of the market, maintaining them in a functional state, as well as in the implementation of the function of a reasonable redistribution of property in the market; - ensuring rational taxation of real estate for the formation of sustainable sources of income for state and local budgets; - implementation of an effective administrative and financial policy in the field of real estate management.

List of used literature:

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